

MODERN AIR CONDITIONING SYSTEMS IN INDUSTRIAL BUILDINGS

M. Ismanxodjayeva^{1,a)}, S. Nurmanov^{1,b)}

¹Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering,

a) Candidate of Technical Sciences, Professor. e-mail: ismanhodzaevam@gmail.com

b) PhD of Technical Sciences, acting associate Professor. e-mail:

sarvar.nurmanov@mail.ru e-mail

Abstract. *The article describes the improvement of the energy efficiency of air conditioning and ventilation systems in industrial buildings. According to the conditions of ensuring high-quality technology in the area of technological equipment, the normalized parameters $t = 25 \pm 0.5$ ° C and relative humidity $fv = 46 \pm 1\%$ are provided all year round in Fig.1. The I-d diagram of humid air shows the construction of the design model of operation of the centrally air conditioning systems in the warm season in the city of Uchkuduk with parameters "B".*

Based on the results of the construction of air treatment processes in the I-d diagram and calculations showed that the use of locally central air conditioning systems leads to an increase in the energy efficiency of systems, as well as energy saving in locally central systems..

Key words: *energy efficiency, technologically comfortable SAC, thermal comfort in the working area, optimal conditions, maintenance functions, sanitary and hygienic requirements, heat surpluses of local cooling devices, significant emissions of dust and gas hazards, local devices, supply and exhaust units, local systems.*

INTRODUCTION

The main factor for the maintenance of the technological process, administrative and household, public, industrial buildings is the maintenance of comfortable conditions.

The requirements of technological air conditioning are based on the production need to maintain certain parameters of the air environment (temperature, humidity and air mobility) during the conduct of many technological processes in various industries, as well as to ensure the operability of electronic equipment, high-precision machines, etc.

The condition of the air is a necessary and decisive condition for the implementation of technological processes.

Air conditioning technology is of great importance in creating a strictly defined temperature and humidity regime at facilities for processing and storing agricultural products, for the preservation of cultural and historical values.

The importance of air conditioning in industrial buildings is increasing from year to year and is becoming more widespread in high-tech industries.

OBJECTS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

The constantly growing requirements for technological comfort air conditioning in industrial buildings leads to the development of energy-efficient circuit diagrams in order to increase energy efficiency and sanitary and hygienic requirements of

ventilation and air conditioning systems.

It is necessary to take into account the specific features of technological processes in the design and development of air conditioning systems carried out in the serviced room.

To maintain a technologically comfortable air conditioning system that supports the required air parameters in the working area of the production process, favorable for the production technology and thermal comfort of people working in the working area. Supported and provided technologically comfortable air conditioning systems, the air parameters do not meet the optimal conditions for maintaining the technological state of a person. In order to achieve optimal conditions and to fulfill the function of ensuring sanitary and hygienic requirements, it is necessary to find out the possibilities of separating technological and comfortable systems.

The operation of the air conditioning system and ensuring energy efficiency in industrial buildings must meet the following requirements:

- by increasing the exhaust air temperature, increase the temperature rise Δt and supply the supply air to the working area;

- to capture contaminants and prevent their spread in the volume of the working area. Places of technological processes should be equipped with local devices;

- strive to use central air conditioners and exhaust systems for the minimum performance required by sanitary standards or technology for supply air;

- technological equipment requiring the maintenance of a special air environment according to the requirements of technologists to allocate to special local systems;

- do not use central recirculation and replace it with local recirculation through local devices with the condition of maintaining the required air environment and the formation of a thermal regime in the serviced area of the production premises;

- use the application in heat exchangers for heating the supply air for the purpose of using the heat of the exhaust air.

RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

To date, central air conditioning systems with central recirculation of internal air and the presence of zonal supply air heaters in separate areas of the room have become the most widespread [7]. However, the use of central recirculation has a number of disadvantages, local central air conditioning systems are more economical and qualitative in terms of the microclimate created. Let's consider the features of traditional central and local-central air conditioning systems on the example of an industrial enterprise.

According to the conditions for ensuring high-quality technology of an industrial building, the following normalized parameters should be maintained in the area of technological equipment all year round [2]: temperature $t_v = 25 \pm 0.5$ °C; relative

humidity $p_v = 46 \pm 1\%$. Fig.1 on the I-d diagram of humid air shows the construction of the design model of operation of the centrally air conditioning systems in the warm period of the year in the city of Uchkuduk with parameters B $t=38.9$ °C; $I=67.4$ kJ/kg [7].

$I=67.4$ kJ/kg. In the workshop of an industrial building, the calculated heat surpluses for apparent heat are 240 kWh, and moisture emissions from 60 employees $W_{v.l.}=60 \times 185=11100$ g/h. Fig.1 shows the possible limits of changes in the internal air parameters required by the workshop technology (point B). From the comparison of the parameters at point B and at point outdoor H, it follows that the enthalpy of indoor air $I_b=49.8$ kJ/kg is less than the enthalpy of outdoor air $I_h=67.4$ kJ/kg. Therefore, in traditional central SLE, central recirculation is used [2]. To maintain the required temperature and relative humidity of the air L_n , the mixture of outdoor and recirculating air L_v must be cooled and dried. According to departmental technological standards, it is necessary to supply 80 m³/h of supply outdoor air for one person working all year round. Then the minimum-unavoidable consumption of supply outdoor air according to the formula will be

$$L_{pn(min)} = 60 \times 80 = 4800 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}.$$

Supply air mixture $(L_n+L_v)=L_n$ must be cooled and drained in the central air conditioner. To absorb heat emissions at an operating temperature difference $\Delta t_{\text{an}}=t_v-t_n=10$ °C, the required supply air flow rate is determined by the following formula

$$L_p = \frac{Q_t \times 3,6}{\rho_n(t_y - t_n) \times c_p} = \frac{240000 \times 3,6}{1,22 \times (25 - 15) \times 1} = 70820 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}.$$

According to traditional recommendations [2], the outdoor air consumption in a mixture with recirculating air should be at least. 10% of the supply air flow:

$$L_{pn} = 0,1 \times 70820 = 8852,4 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}.$$

The working difference in the perception of moisture emissions in the workshop will be

$$\Delta d_{ac} = \frac{11100}{70820} = 0,126 \text{ g/kg}.$$

Or the moisture content of the supply air should be

$$\Delta d_{ac} = d_B - \Delta d_{ac} = 9,8 - 0,126 = 9,674 \text{ g/kg}.$$

Fig.1. Construction on the I-d diagram of the calculated modes of operation of the central air conditioning system with variable recirculation in the warm and cold periods of the year in the city of Uchkuduk in the workshop of an industrial building

The parameters of the mixture of outdoor and recirculating air correspond to the point CM: $t_{\text{ni}} = 26 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $d_{\text{ni}} = 10,2 \text{ g/kg}$; $I_{\text{ni}} = 52 \text{ kJ/kg}$. To implement the cooling and dehumidification mode of the supply air in the surface air cooler at the initial humidity of the air $\varphi_{\text{ni}} = 24\%$ it is possible to cool the supply air mixture to $\varphi_{\text{i}\bar{o}} = 85\%$ [5].

At the intersection of $\varphi_{\text{i}\bar{o}} = 85\%$ and $d_p = 8,08 \text{ g/kg}$, we find the parameters of cooled and drained supply air $t_{\text{i}\bar{o}} = 13 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $I_{\text{i}\bar{o}} = 33,6 \text{ kJ/kg}$.

The cold consumption for cooling the supply air mixture in the air cooler of the central air conditioner will be

$$Q_x = L_p \times \rho_p \times \frac{I_{\text{CM}} - I_{\text{ox}}}{3,6} = 70820 \times 1,22 \times \frac{52 - 33,6}{3,6} = 441602 \text{ Wt.}$$

In the fan and supply air ducts, the cooled supply air will be heated by $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. To obtain the required inflow temperature $t_p = 15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, it is necessary to consume heat in the second heating coil

$$Q_{\text{кал. II}} = L_p \times \rho_p \times \frac{t_{\text{CM}} - t_{\text{ox.I}}}{3,6} = 70820 \times 1,21 \times \frac{15 - 14}{3,6} = 23803 \text{ Wt.}$$

Even on the settlement day of the warm period of the year, the heat surpluses in the shop can vary from 100% to 40%. In order to maintain the air parameters required by the technology (point B), the temperature control sensor acts on an automatic valve that provides an increase in the thermal performance of the second heating heater with

a decrease in the $Q_{t, isb}$ in the shop.

During the cold period of the year, traditional central air conditioning systems did not use exhaust air heat recovery units for heating the supply outdoor air. Unfortunately, this trend continues to this day. Therefore, the left side of Fig. 1 shows the operating modes of the SCR under the calculated conditions of the cold period of the year without the use of a recycling unit. The minimum heating of the supply outside air, according to the conditions of safety against freezing, can be taken as $t_{eI}=5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.. By mixing the external and internal recirculating air heated to enthalpy $I_{eI}=5,9\text{ kJ/kg}$, $I_v = 49.8\text{ kJ/kg}$, it is necessary to obtain the 1 enthalpy of the mixture $I_{cm} = 38.22\text{ kJ/kg}$, which is a controlled parameter during year-round operation of the air conditioning and air conditioning system with accurate and constant maintenance of air parameters in the working area (point B). From the mixture balance equation, we obtain an expression for finding the required flow rate of heated outdoor air:

$$L_{pn} = \frac{L_p(I_B - I_{cm})}{I_B - I_{KI}} = \frac{70820 \times (67,4 - 38,2)}{67,4 - 5,9} = 33407,8\text{ m}^3/h.$$

The recirculating air consumption in the design conditions of the cold period will be

$$L_B = L_{II} - L_{IIH} = 70820 - 33407,8 = 37412,2\text{ m}^3/h.$$

The calculation showed that due to the need to obtain the required constant enthalpy of the mixture $I_{cm} = 38.22\text{ kJ/kg}$ in the cold period of the year, it is necessary to increase the flow of supply outdoor air in the mixture. This will require the use of automatic adjustable air valves in the outside air intake pipes, in the connection pipe to the exhaust unit of the recirculation duct and in the exhaust pipe of the exhaust air L_y into the atmosphere. Such an automatic control unit complicates the air conditioning and ventilation systems and requires constant monitoring and adjustment.

On the left side of Fig. 1 shows the construction on the diagram of humid air of the operation mode of the central air conditioning system at parameters B in the city of Uchkuduk $t_n=-16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $I=-14.2\text{ kJ/kg}$.

The heat consumption in the heater of the first heating will be:

$$Q_{kall} = 33408 \times 1,3 \times \frac{5 + 16}{3,6} = \frac{43430 \times 21}{3,6} = 43430 \times 5,83 = 253342\text{ Wt}$$

As a result of mixing the heated and recirculating air, we obtain the parameters at the point CM. $t_{cm} = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$; $t_{cm} = 13,2^{\circ}\text{C}$; $I = 39,4\text{ kJ/kg}$.

To achieve the air parameters at the points, it is necessary to moisten the resulting mixture of supply air adiabatically. Technological blocks with an irrigated layer of hygroscopic material have the best energy indicator in adiabatic humidification modes.

The effectiveness of adiabatic humidification is evaluated by the indicator:

$$E_a = \frac{t_{CM} - t_{OX}}{t_{CM} - t_{CM.M}} = \frac{20 - 14,5}{20 - 13,2} = 0,95$$

Irrigated layers with a depth of 500 mm provide the required indicator of the effectiveness of adiabatic humidification. In the supply duct and the fan, we take heating at 1 °C and then we get $t_{CM1} = 15,5^{\circ}\text{C}$. In the cold period of the fence and in the absence of solar radiation, the calculated heat surpluses are 68 kWt.h. we calculate the required supply air temperature to absorb the calculated heat surpluses in the cold period of the year:

$$t_{nx} = t_v \times \frac{Q_{t.izb} \times 3600}{L_n \times \rho_n \times c_p};$$

For our example under consideration, using the formula (2) we obtain:

$$t_{nx} = 25 \times \frac{98 \times 3600}{70820 \times 122 \times 1} = 21^{\circ}\text{C}.$$

In the heater of the first heating or in zone heaters, the amount of heat is consumed in the calculated mode:

$$Q_{kalII} = 38577 \times 1,22 \times 1 \times \frac{20 - 15,2}{3,6} = 47064 \text{ Wt}$$

The total heat consumption in air conditioning systems in the design mode of the cold period is equal to.

$$\sum Q_{tsjv} = Q_{kalI} + Q_{kalII} = 253342 + 47064 = 300406 \text{ Wt}$$

CONCLUSION

The calculations and analysis performed show that in traditional central air conditioning systems, cold is initially spent on cooling and dehumidifying the supply air, and then, to maintain the air parameters required by the technology in the working area, heat is consumed in the second heating heater. When designing ACS for workshops of a large area and the presence of production sites with heat releases that vary with the time of day, they resort to the use of multi-zone ACS. From the common supply manifold, several supply outlets are supplied to the workshop. A zonal air heater is mounted on each outlet, controlled from a control sensor in each serviced area of the workshop.

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